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Research Article

AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF RICE MILK UPON MENOPAUSAL SYMPTOMS AMONG MENOPAUSAL WOMEN ADMITTED IN SELECTED HOSPITAL, KALABURAGI.

¹Dr. Vidyashree,* ²Dr. Savita Dankur and ³Shabnoor Khanam

MAM College of Pharmacy, Kalaburagi, Karnataka, India.^{1,3}

Vishwaradhya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Abbetumkur, Yadgir, Karnataka, India.²

Abstract:

Women's health is a matrix of many factors relating to fertility, sexuality, and societal conditions that affect health. Traditionally, in the years between menarche and menopause, women's health needs have largely been related to fertility. With higher levels of education and participation in the workforce and other societal changes. The health of the women is an important component not only during reproductive years but also throughout the course of her life. Due to hormonal changes women notice hot flush, night sweat, insomnia, vasomotor changes. They may vary in intensity from a barely perceptible warm feeling to sensation of extreme warmth accompanied by profuse sweating, causing discomfort, sleep disturbance and subsequent fatigue. The entire Genito urinary system is affected by the reduced oestrogen level. Changes in the vulvo vaginal area may include a gradual thinning of pubic hair and a gradual shrinkage of the labia. Vaginal secretions decrease and women may report dyspareunia. The medical treatment for menopausal symptoms is hormonal replacement therapy. It improving the quality of life of menopausal women by reducing menopausal symptoms and osteoporosis, but there is chance to increase the risk of developing certain malignancies in particularly breast and gynaecological cancers. Therefore, the main objective of the present study is to assess the Effectiveness of rice milk upon Menopausal symptoms among Menopausal women.

Samples consists of 60 Menopausal women, who was admitted in selected hospital and those postnatal mothers who satisfies the inclusion criteria are considered as samples. Content validity is done with the help of experts. Split- Half method is used to check the reliability. The evaluation includes the effect of Rice milk upon Menopausal symptoms among Menopausal women, and associate the knowledge with selected demographic variable among Menopausal women. The mean 20.16 of post-test score was more than the mean 18.09 of pre-test score of Menopausal women. There is total enhancement occur 02.7. The comparison of before administration and after administration of Rice milk's effect upon Menopausal symptoms among Menopausal women that the mean, standard deviation of level of knowledge regarding menopause and menopausal management were same ($M=5.23$, $SD=1.66$) in control and experimental group menopausal women. The difference was not statistically significant at $p<0.05$ level of confidence. The results from this study found that the effectiveness of rice milk upon menopausal symptoms in experimental group was better than those in the control group.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Vidyashree,

MAM College of Pharmacy,

Kalaburagi, Karnataka, India

QR CODE

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INTRODUCTION:

Menopause is the time in a woman's life when her periods stop as a result of the reduction and loss of 'ovarian reproductive function'. Ovaries produce the hormones oestrogen, progesterone and testosterone. When a woman approaches the menopause, less oestrogen is produced causing her body to behave differently. This process is usually a gradual one that progresses over several years. Oestrogen also plays an important role in maintaining bone and heart health as well as brain function during the reproductive years. (1-11)

Women play an important role in replenishing the earth but her reproductive capacity is not permanent it ceases one day. The cessation of reproductive capacity is coined as "menopause".

Rice milk, it is a plant-based beverage made from brown rice, which is cultivated globally, primarily in Asia. brown rice, can support menopause by providing complex carbs for stable energy (reducing hot flashes) and fiber. The beneficial effects of other areas include reducing the cardio vascular risk through their beneficial effects. (12-20)

RESEARCH STATEMENT

"An Experimental Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Rice milk upon Menopausal symptoms among Menopausal women admitted in selected hospital, Kalaburagi."

AIM OF THE STUDY

To Assess the Effectiveness of Rice milk upon Menopausal symptoms among Menopausal women and increase the level of knowledge on Rice milk uses upon Menopausal symptoms.

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the prevalence of menopausal symptoms among menopausal women.

S No	Demographic variables	Control group n =30		Experimental group n =30	
		N	P	N	P
1	Age in years				
	40 – 45	1	-	-	-
	46-50	6	36.67	8	26.67
	51-55	4	36.67	13	43.33
	Above 55	9	26.67	9	30.00
2	Marital Status				
	Married	19	100.0	29	96.67
	Unmarried	-	-	-	-
	Widow	-	-	1	3.33
3	Educational qualification				
	Illiterate	6	20.00	4	13.33
	Primary	19	63.33	21	70.00
	Higher Secondary	5	16.67	5	16.67
4	Income in the family (in rupees)				
	Below 5000	3	10.00	3	10.00
	5001 – 10000	10	33.33	17	56.7
	10001 – 15000	6	20.00	10	33.33
	Above 15000	4	13.33	7	23.33
5	Occupation				
	Homemaker	27	90.00	24	80.00
	Self employed	3	10.00	6	20.00
	Employed	-	-	-	-
6	Nature of work				
	Sedentary work	-	-	1	3.33
	Moderate work	30	100.00	22	73.33
	Heavy work	-	-	7	23.33

- To assess the level of knowledge regarding menopause in control and experimental group of menopausal women.
- To determine the effectiveness of Rice milk by comparing the menopausal symptoms in control and experimental group of menopausal women.

- To identify the association between selected demographic variables and the menopausal symptoms in control and experimental group before and after administration of Rice milk.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Approach	Quantitative Approach
Research Design	Experimental research design
Research Setting	GIMS Hospital, Kalaburagi.
Population	Menopausal women of Kalaburagi.
Target population	Menopausal women with menopausal symptoms.
Sample Size	The sample size was 30 in both groups.
Sample Technique	Simple random sampling

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION DATA SECTION- I

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Demographic Variables in the Control and Experimental Group of Menopausal Women. N=0

Table Reveals: -

The data in table revealed that, majority of the menopausal women were married (100%, 96.67%), educated up to primary school (63.33%, 70%), home-makers (90%, 80%), moderate workers (100%, 73%). Significant percentage of them were between the age of 51-55 years (36.67%, 43.33%) with monthly income Rs10000 and above (33.33%, 56.67%) in control and experimental group respectively. family & relatives and 4(13.3%) were having knowledge from others.

SECTION- II

Comparison of Mean and Standard deviation of Knowledge Regarding Menopause in the Control and Experimental group of Menopausal Women. (N=60)

Groups	Knowledge about menopause			Knowledge about menopausal management		
	Mean	SD	t	Mean	SD	T
Control	5.23	1.66	0.16	5.33	1.61	0.48
Experimental	5.06	1.69		5.16	1.71	

Significant at < 0.05% level

Table revealed that the mean, standard deviation of level of knowledge regarding menopause and menopausal management were same (M=5.23, SD=1.66) in control and experimental group menopausal women. The difference was not statistically significant at p<0.05% level of confidence.

SECTION- III

Association Between selected Demographic Variables and Menopausal symptoms Before and After Administration of Rice milk in Experimental group of menopausal women. (N=30)

S No.	Demographic Variables	Before Administration			After Administration		
		Moderate	Severe	χ^2	Mild	Moderate	χ^2
1	Age in years			3.681(df=3)			9.487* (d.f = 3)
	40 – 45	1	-		1	-	
	46-50	6	1		7	-	
	51-55	4	5		3	6	
	Above 55	9	4	10	3		
2	Marital Status			0.517 (d.f = 1)			0.443 (d.f = 1)
	Married	19	10		20	9	
	Unmarried	-	-		-	-	
	Widow	1	-		1	-	

3	Educational Qualification					
	Illiterate	1	3	4.37 (d.f = 3)	2	2
	Primary	7	3		8	3
Higher Secondary	3	2	3		2	
						4.48 (d.f = 3)
3	Income in the family (in rupees)					
	Below 5000	3	0	3.681 (d.f = 3)	3	-
	5001 – 10000	9	1		8	4
	10001 –15000	3	7		4	6
Above 15000	5	2	6		1	
						6.871 (d.f = 3)
4	Occupation					
	Homemaker	16	8	2.400 (d.f = 2)	17	7
	Self employed	4	2		4	2
Employed	-	-	-		-	
						2.579 (d.f = 2)
5	Nature of work					
	Sedentary work	1	-	0.662 (d.f = 2)	1	-
	Moderate work	14	8		15	7
Heavy work	5	2	5		2	
						0.470 (d.f = 2)

The researcher calculated the value of chi square in order to find out the association that there was a significant association between selected demographic variables such as age of menopausal women and menopausal symptoms at ($p < 0.05$) hence null hypotheses Ho2. “There will be no significant association between selected demographic variables and menopausal symptoms in control and experimental group of menopausal women” was rejected.

However, there was no significant association between other demographic variables such as marital status, education, occupation, nature of work, income of menopausal women and menopausal symptoms at ($p < 0.05$), hence null hypotheses Ho2 was retained.

DISCUSSION:

This chapter dealt with findings of the present study, “An Experimental Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Rice milk upon Menopausal symptoms among Menopausal women in Selected admitted in selected hospital, Kalaburagi.” In this chapter, an attempt has been made to discuss the findings of other studies. The present study was conducted in the GIMS Hospital, Kalaburagi. Total sample was 60 Menopausal women who were admitted in the hospital. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample. Before returning collecting the data, the investigator introduce herself, explained the purpose of the study and obtained written consent. Socio demographic was used to collect personal information of subjects and experiment was done to assess Effectiveness of Rice milk upon Menopausal symptoms among Menopausal women.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of the study showed that the effectiveness of Rice milk upon menopausal symptoms in experimental group was better than those in the control group. Hence it could be concluded that there is an association between the menopausal symptoms and administration of Rice milk. Rice milk is easy to administer and a natural supplement for menopausal women, which can also be prepared at home and consumed.

MEDICAL IMPLICATIONS

The present study emphasized regarding knowledge on selected aspects of Essential newborn care among postnatal mothers.

- Pharmacy Practice.
- administration
- Research
- Education

RECOMMENDATIONS

- The same study could be conducted on larger sample for better generalization.
- The study could be replicated in hospitals for hysterectomy clients.
- A study can be conducted on effectiveness of alternative therapies in reducing the severity of menopausal symptoms.
- A study needs to be carried out in the urban and rural areas to find out the difference in knowledge.

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